

Reinforcement Learning-Based Trust Dynamics Prediction Model for Teleoperated Human-Robot Interaction

Juan Jose Garcia Cardenas¹ and Adriana Tapus¹

Abstract—Trust plays a crucial role in user performance during teleoperated human-robot interaction. This study presents a reinforcement learning (RL) model that adapts to dynamic trust levels using physiological data and task performance metrics. Participants completed a complex teleoperation task under three conditions: (C1) limited feedback, (C2) AI-generated verbal guidance, and (C3) AI guidance paired with real-time RViz visualization. Physiological indicators, such as blink rate, galvanic skin response (GSR), and facial temperature along with task performance metrics like success rate and completion time were tracked. Statistical analyses revealed that increased task complexity in C1 reduced trust and increased cognitive load, leading to poorer performance. AI-generated guidance in C2 improved task understanding and performance, supporting Hypothesis H2. In C3, combining AI guidance with RViz visualization further boosted trust and reduced cognitive load, partially confirming Hypothesis H3. The RL model successfully adapted guidance strategies based on real-time user states, and additional testing showed that the agent’s adaptive strategies significantly increased user trust and improved performance. These results underscore the potential of adaptive RL models to enhance trust and efficiency in teleoperated human-robot systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Human-Robot Interaction (HRI), the dynamic nature of trust between humans and robotic systems plays a crucial role in ensuring effective collaboration, particularly in teleoperation tasks within hazardous environments such as nuclear facilities and rescue operations [1], [2]. As robots are increasingly deployed in these environments to protect human workers, understanding how trust changes over time becomes critical. Human operators depend significantly on robotic feedback, and the degree of trust they place in the system can directly influence both task efficiency and safety. In the domain of trust estimation in Human-Robot Interaction (HRI), numerous models have been developed to capture the dynamic nature of trust as it evolves during interactions. Probabilistic models, including Bayesian networks, have been widely used to predict trust based on user behavior, system feedback, and task performance [3], [4]. These models allow for real-time adjustments to system behavior, improving user trust by adapting to the user’s needs throughout the task. Reinforcement learning (RL) has also been proposed as a promising approach for trust estimation,

particularly in cases where trust evolves based on repeated interactions with the robot. RL-based models can optimize system actions by learning from previous interactions and predicting trust outcomes, allowing for more responsive and adaptive systems in complex teleoperation scenarios [5]. Researchers have increasingly recognized the importance of incorporating both user feedback and physiological data to more accurately estimate trust, making the models robust to a variety of task conditions.

During teleoperation, operators experience different levels of cognitive load, which refers to the mental effort needed to process information, make decisions, and control the robot. In HRI, cognitive load is shaped by various factors such as task complexity, user experience, and the design of the interface used to interact with the robot [6]. Managing cognitive load is essential, as excessive demands can hinder performance and diminish trust in the system. Additionally, interface design plays a key role in reducing cognitive load, enabling smoother interactions between the operator and the robot. Multi-modal feedback, such as haptic and visual cues, has been implemented to improve operator control and task success, but many challenges remain in ensuring reliable operation under these high-stress conditions [7], [8]. As the complexity of tasks increases, the strain on the operator also intensifies, requiring advancements in control interfaces and feedback mechanisms to maintain operator efficiency and safety [9].

A key focus of this study is the understanding that trust is dynamic, evolving as users engage with the system and re-calibrate their expectations based on its performance and feedback [4]. Objective insights into the cognitive demands on the user are provided by tools such as the NASA TLX [10], as well as physiological measures like Galvanic Skin Response (GSR), facial temperature, and blink rate [11].

In this work, we integrate Generative AI (Gen AI) to provide intuitive verbal guidance alongside visual feedback through the RViz robotic visualization system [12]. This combined approach is designed to improve task comprehension, reduce cognitive load, and dynamically adjust trust over time. Recent studies on Gen AI’s role in robotics highlight its potential to enhance human-robot collaboration by delivering real-time, adaptive guidance [13], [14]. Furthermore, we introduce a Reinforcement Learning (RL) model that predicts trust dynamically based on physiological and performance metrics. This RL-based trust prediction method is validated as a novel approach for optimizing trust dynamics in teleoperated robotic systems [5] [3].

The paper is structured as follows: Our experimental

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¹Juan Jose Garcia Cardenas is a Phd candidate of U2IS, ENSTA, Institut Polytechnique de Paris, Paris, France juan-jose.garcia@ensta.fr

¹Adriana Tapus is a Full Professor in the Autonomous Systems and Robotics Lab/U2IS, ENSTA, Institut Polytechnique de Paris, Paris, France adriana.tapus@ensta.fr

design and the model approach are detailed in Section II and the results are detailed in Section IV. Finally, conclusions and insights into future research directions are provided in Section V.

II. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

A. Robotic Platform and Sensors

In this work, we used the UR5 manipulator robot [15] mounted on a Husky mobile robotic platform [16] as shown in Figure 1. The UR5, a 6-axis lightweight arm, offers a payload of 5 kg, a reach of 850 mm, a precision of ± 0.1 mm, and is equipped with an intuitive programming interface and advanced safety features, making it ideal for precise manipulation tasks [15]. Teleoperation is facilitated through a 6-degree-of-freedom joystick, providing intuitive and accurate control over the UR5's movements, which is critical for investigating the operator's cognitive load. We used RGB and thermal cameras to record participants' facial features during the experiment. The RGB camera is a Logitech HD webcam C930e (1080p, 30FPS), and the thermal camera is an Optris PI 640i USB-powered Infrared Camera (640x480, 32FPS, temperature range -20°C ~ 100°C). These two cameras were fixed on an octopus tripod. The experimental setup is shown in Figure 1. The OptiTrack system is essential for providing precise 6-DoF tracking of all key elements in the experiment.

To assess cognitive load during the teleoperation experiments, we employed **noninvasive physiological sensors**, particularly galvanic skin response (GSR) units, which are well-suited for monitoring skin conductance. We used the Shimmer3 GSR+ units [17]. With a sampling rate adjustable up to 128 Hz, the devices effectively capture subtle GSR fluctuations, offering valuable insight into the cognitive challenges posed by the teleoperation tasks. GSR has proven effective in various settings for measuring physiological and cognitive responses, providing reliable data without the discomfort associated with invasive techniques like cardio-respiratory monitoring [18], [19]. This setup ensures the accurate and comfortable measurement of cognitive load throughout the experiment.

B. Subjective Measures

Participants were required to complete multiple questionnaires throughout the experiment.

1) *Spatial Orientation Test (SOT)*: The Spatial Orientation Test (SOT) assesses participants' perspective-taking ability, which is crucial for task performance in teleoperation. It consists of 12 items that evaluate spatial visualization, requiring participants to mentally determine directions to targets without physical rotation [20]. Higher error scores indicate lower spatial ability.

2) *NASA Task Load Index (TLX)*: Following each condition, participants completed the NASA-TLX [10], a subjective workload assessment tool that measures cognitive load across six dimensions: Mental, Physical, and Temporal Demands, Performance, Effort, and Frustration, using a 20-point scale.

3) *Human-Robot Trust Scale (HRTS)*: Participants completed the Human-Robot Trust Scale (HRTS) after each condition to evaluate their trust in the robot [21], measuring reliability, predictability, and competence to reveal how guidance and information levels affect trust.

C. Scenario

Participants engage in a multi-task scenario involving navigation and object manipulation. Their goal is to find and retrieve an object from a random location in a complex environment and place it in a designated safe zone within 5 minutes. The task utilizes a UR5 robotic arm mounted on a Husky mobile robot. Participants first navigate the mobile robot through obstacles, then switch to controlling the robotic arm to pick up and place the object.

In the experimental setup, participants are positioned behind a wall, blocking their direct view of the robot's movements. This design ensures they rely entirely on visual feedback and guidance during the task. The environment features designated pick and goal zones, as well as obstacles the robot must avoid. Participants must guide the robot along a specified path to complete the task. Figure 2 shows the layout, including the participant's position, the pick and goal zones, the object to be retrieved, and the robot's path through the environment.

The task will be conducted under three different conditions, allowing for an evaluation of the participant's performance and cognitive load in various guidance and feedback setups. The detailed conditions are outlined below:

- **C1**: Participants control the robot via a graphical user interface (GUI) showing live video from three camera angles. After two minutes, the live feed freezes, leaving only the last captured frames. Participants then have three minutes to complete the task using these static images.
- **C2**: Similar to C1, participants use a GUI showing live feeds from three cameras, which freeze after two minutes, retaining the last images. In addition to the static visuals, they receive real-time verbal guidance from a generative AI system. This AI provides adaptive instructions based on the robot's and participant's actions. The generative AI system used in this condition is based on the OpenAI GPT-4 model [22], configured to generate concise, task-relevant instructions constrained to a maximum of 15 words to ensure clarity and prevent information overload. Participants have three minutes to complete the task with the assistance of the AI guidance.
- **C3**: Expanding on C2, participants not only have frozen images and generative AI guidance but also access real-time robot positional data displayed in RViz on their GUI. The robot's components are visualized as groups of reflective spheres, assisting in planning and execution. Figure 3 provides an example of how RViz feedback is integrated into the interface. Using this enhanced GUI, participants must complete the task within the remaining three minutes after the video feed freezes.

Fig. 1. Experimental setup: The participant operates the UR5 mounted on the Husky robot using a 3D mouse and the MoveIt package for inverse kinematics. Two cameras record the temperature and blinking rate of the user throughout the experiment. The Optitrack system records the real-time positions of the items in the scene. The user has access to a GUI for guidance, powered by GEN AI

Fig. 2. Experimental task to complete

D. Task Performance and User's Modelling

We evaluate each participant's performance by recording the success rate and the time taken to complete the task in each condition. To monitor physiological responses, we measure facial temperature across different regions using a thermal camera and the `dlib` Python library [23], capturing data at 125 frames per second. Blink rate per minute (specifically Action Unit 45) is tracked using an RGB camera and the `OpenFace` library [24]. Additionally, we measure Galvanic Skin Response (GSR) with sensors placed on two fingers and the ear of each participant. These combined measurements provide a comprehensive assessment of both task performance and user behavior during the experiment.

E. Reinforcement Learning Trust Model

To dynamically manage trust and cognitive load during the teleoperation task, we model the interaction as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) with the following components:

1) *States (S)*: Each state $s \in S$ captures a comprehensive snapshot of the user's psychological, physiological, and task-related status:

- **Trust Level (T)**: The current estimated level of trust the user has in the system [21].

- **Cognitive Load (CL)**: Assessed through physiological indicators:
 - **Facial Temperature (FT)**: Variations that reflect stress or cognitive load.
 - **Blink Rate (BR)**: Blinks per minute, an indicator of cognitive load and stress.
 - **Galvanic Skin Response (GSR)**: Skin conductance reflecting emotional arousal.
- **Spatial Orientation Test Score (SOT)**: Evaluates the user's spatial reasoning abilities [25].
- **Task Performance Metrics (P)**: Including success rate and task completion time.

The connection between these measures and trust dynamics is grounded in human factors and psychology research. Trust, a psychological construct, influences user interaction with automated systems and is measured using the Human-Robot Trust Scale (HRTS) [21], assessing reliability, predictability, and competence. Cognitive load is inferred from physiological indicators: increased facial temperature (notably in the nose and forehead) correlates with higher cognitive load and stress [?]; elevated blink rates indicate increased cognitive load [?]; and higher GSR reflects greater emotional arousal, a proxy for cognitive load [?]. The SOT score measures spatial reasoning critical for navigation and manipulation tasks [25], while task performance metrics (success rate and completion time) reflect user effectiveness, modulated by trust and cognitive load.

2) *Actions (A)*: The agent's actions are adjustments made between task conditions to optimize trust, performance, and cognitive load. The available actions are:

- 1) **Increase Verbal Guidance** (Applicable in C2 and C3): Offer more detailed instructions when high cognitive load or low trust is detected, increasing from 2 to 3 instructions per request. This action increases the number of instructions by one per application, starting from a baseline (e.g., 2 instructions) up to a maximum of 3 instructions. If the maximum of 3 is reached, further applications of this action have no effect until the number of instructions is reduced by "Decrease

Trust HRI Experiments - RL Model - Condition 3

Fig. 3. Condition C3: Image freezing, AI guidance, and RViz Visualization

Verbal Guidance.”

Examples:

- “Turn left to avoid the obstacle.”
- “Pick up the bottle from the table.”

- 2) **Decrease Verbal Guidance** (Applicable in C2 and C3): Provide less detailed instructions to promote autonomy if high trust and low cognitive load are observed. Decrease from 2 to 1 instruction per request. This action decreases the number of instructions by one per application, down to a minimum of 1 instruction. If the minimum of 1 is reached, further applications of this action have no effect until the number of instructions is increased by “Increase Verbal Guidance.”

Examples:

- “Move the robot toward the object at the pick zone”
- “Now, move the object to the goal zone and drop it.”

- 3) **Simplify Visual Interface** (Applicable in C3): Reduce visual complexity by hiding less critical elements if a high cognitive load is detected. Display only essential components: mobile robot, object to place, and goal zone. Each application of this action hides one additional non-essential element (e.g., obstacles, secondary markers) incrementally until only the essential components remain. If applied consecutively, the interface simplifies further with each step until

the minimal configuration is reached, after which no further simplification occurs.

Example:

- The interface hides obstacles and the pick zone to reduce visual clutter.

- 4) **Enhance Visual Interface** (Applicable in C3): Provide more detailed visual information if the user shows high trust and efficiency. Display all 7 rigid bodies, including obstacles. Each application of this action reveals one additional element (e.g., obstacles, additional markers) in a incrementally, up to a maximum of 7 rigid bodies. If applied consecutively, the interface becomes progressively more detailed until all elements are displayed, after which no further enhancement occurs.

Example:

- The interface shows a full overview of the environment, aiding in complex planning.

- 5) **Provide Tutorial or Tips** (Applicable in C2 and C3): Offer a brief tutorial or tips before the next condition if the user struggles with specific tasks. This action is restricted to a single application per condition transition, delivering one set of tips or a tutorial segment. Consecutive applications within the same transition are not permitted.

Examples:

- “Remember, you can use the joystick to move the robot in any direction”
- “To avoid obstacles, make slow and steady movements.”

3) *Transition Function* ($P(s' | s, a)$): The transition function models the probability of moving from state s to state s' given action a :

$$P(s' | s, a) = \Pr\{S_{m+1} = s' | S_m = s, A_m = a\} \quad (1)$$

The agent’s actions affect the user’s cognitive load, trust, and performance. Initially, actions are chosen with equal probability. As the agent learns from user responses, it updates its policy to select actions that are more likely to result in favorable state transitions, enhancing the effectiveness of the guidance strategies.

To ensure model stability and address variability, we implemented several strategies:

- **Experience Replay:** Experiences are stored in a replay buffer, allowing the model to learn from diverse past interactions, reducing sequential correlations and stabilizing training.
- **Target Networks:** Used in the SAC algorithm for both actor and critic, these networks are updated slowly to provide consistent targets, enhancing training stability.
- **Hyperparameter Tuning:** A grid search over learning rates, batch sizes, and entropy coefficients identified optimal settings for stable convergence.
- **Early Stopping:** Training was halted when performance on a validation set stabilized, preventing overfitting.
- **Averaged Results:** Multiple training sessions with different random seeds were averaged to account for performance variability due to stochastic user responses and environmental factors.
- **Outlier Handling:** Outliers in physiological data were removed using the interquartile range (IQR) method, with thresholds at 1.5 times the IQR, to prevent extreme values from skewing training.

4) *Reward Function* ($R(s, a)$): The reward function integrates trust improvement, performance enhancement, and cognitive load management. It is defined as:

$$R(s, a) = W_T \cdot \Delta T + W_P \cdot (\Delta SR + \Delta TE) - W_{CL} \cdot \Delta CL \quad (2)$$

where ΔT represents the change in trust level between conditions, ΔSR and ΔTE capture improvements in task success rate and completion time, respectively, and ΔCL is the change in cognitive load (with a negative sign indicating that reducing cognitive load is beneficial). The weights W_T , W_P , and W_{CL} represent the importance of trust, performance, and cognitive load, respectively. For this trust-centered task, we set $W_T = 0.5$, $W_P = 0.25$, and $W_{CL} = 0.25$. The reward is calculated after the user completes each condition, as post-condition data is required to compute the changes in trust, performance, and cognitive load. These weights are fixed to

normalize the reward and reflect the emphasis on trust in this task, although future work could involve tuning them for optimal performance.

The reward function balances multiple objectives:

- **Trust Improvement** (ΔT): Encourages actions that boost user trust, critical for effective human-robot interaction.
- **Performance Enhancement** ($\Delta SR + \Delta TE$): Rewards actions improving success rate and reducing completion time for efficient task execution.
- **Cognitive Load Management** ($-\Delta CL$): Penalizes actions increasing cognitive load to maintain manageable user workload.

The weights $W_T = 0.5$, $W_P = 0.25$, and $W_{CL} = 0.25$ were selected based on preliminary experiments to normalize reward components, prioritizing trust as the primary focus.

5) *Learning Process and Algorithm Choice:* Due to the batch feedback nature of the environment, we implement a learning strategy involving data collection, offline training, and a replay buffer. Data is gathered throughout the experiments, including state transitions, actions taken, and rewards received after each condition. Since real-time updates are impractical, the agent is trained offline using the collected data. Experiences are stored in a replay buffer, enabling the agent to learn from a wide range of experiences and reduce correlations between sequential data samples.

We employ the Soft Actor-Critic (SAC) algorithm from the Stable Baselines library for several reasons [26]. SAC is an off-policy algorithm, meaning it can learn from data collected by any policy, which is beneficial for using the replay buffer and learning from the batch data collected during experiments. Off-policy algorithms like SAC are more sample-efficient, making better use of the collected data. Additionally, SAC can handle the stochastic nature of user responses in human-robot interaction tasks and is well-suited for continuous action spaces, aligning with the adjustments we need to make in the guidance strategies.

The RL evaluation involved five participants due to the resource-intensive nature of collecting physiological data and the need for extensive offline training. Performance results (80% success rate, 3 minutes 35 seconds average completion time) were similar to C2 (77.8% success rate, 3 minutes 43 seconds). However, the RL model’s ability to dynamically adjust guidance based on real-time user states offers potential for more consistent performance across diverse users and conditions. Future work will include a larger study with at least 18 participants (matching the baseline study), comparing the RL model to static guidance strategies (e.g., constant verbal feedback) to highlight dynamic adjustment benefits, and analyzing additional metrics like user satisfaction and perceived trust.

By structuring the reinforcement learning model this way and selecting SAC for its benefits in offline, off-policy learning, we aim to develop an adaptive system that tailors to individual user needs, improving both trust and performance in teleoperated human-robot interaction.

III. HYPOTHESIS

Based on research in collaborative human-robot interaction (HRI) and trust modeling, we have proposed the following hypotheses for our user study:

- **H1:** Increased task complexity, as represented by reduced support in the teleoperation interface, will negatively affect user trust and cognitive load, resulting in lower success rates and longer completion times. Research indicates that higher task complexity raises cognitive load and diminishes trust in automation, which in turn leads to decreased task performance [27], [28].
- **H2:** Using AI-generated guidance in C2 will lead to improved task comprehension and performance compared to the condition without this guidance (C1). Research indicates that AI-driven guidance systems improve user comprehension and task performance in complex scenarios [29], [30].
- **H3:** Combining AI-generated guidance with real-time RViz visualization in C3 is expected to increase user trust and decrease cognitive load compared to the other conditions (C1 and C2). Research has shown that such a combination enhances user trust and reduces the cognitive load in HRI tasks [31], [32].
- **H4:** In the context of adaptive guidance, such as provided by the reinforcement learning (RL) model, trust in the system will increase dynamically for the task as the guidance is customized to the user's current state. Trust is dynamic and evolves with user experience and system reliability, increasing over time with consistent guidance [33], [34].

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Participants

Eighteen individuals participated in this experiment, comprising 7 females and 11 males, who are students at Institut Polytechnique de Paris (IP Paris). Their ages range from 18 to 26 years (12 participants, 40%), from 26 to 30 years (3 participants, 55%), and above 30 years (3 participants, 5%), respectively. Given the relatively small sample size, the findings may not be applicable to larger or more diverse populations or other contexts.

B. General Performance

In terms of general performance, significant differences were observed across the three conditions. In Condition 1 (C1), only 5 out of 18 participants (27.8%) successfully completed the task, with an average completion time of 4 minutes and 39 seconds. In Condition 2 (C2), the success rate increased markedly to 14 out of 18 participants (77.8%), and the average completion time decreased to 3 minutes and 43 seconds. In Condition 3 (C3), 9 out of 18 participants (50%) completed the task successfully, with an average completion time of 4 minutes and 14 seconds.

A one-way ANOVA revealed a significant effect of condition on task performance, $F(2, 51) = 251.2, p < 0.001$. These results indicate statistically significant differences

across conditions, partially supporting Hypothesis H1, which posits that increased task complexity negatively impacts user performance, as shown by the lower success rates and longer completion times in C1. The notably better performance in C2 compared to C1 suggests that the generative AI guidance helped participants navigate the complex multi-task scenario more effectively, underscoring its value in enhancing user performance in complex teleoperation tasks. A Games-Howell post-hoc test between C1 and C2 confirmed a significant difference, $p < 0.001$, supporting Hypothesis H2 by demonstrating that AI-generated guidance can improve performance in complex tasks.

However, the performance in C3 (50% success rate) was lower than in C2 (77.8%), despite C3 including both AI guidance and RViz visualization. A post-hoc Games-Howell test between C2 and C3 revealed a significant difference in success rates ($p = 0.012$), indicating that the addition of RViz in C3 did not enhance performance as anticipated in H3. This suggests that RViz may have introduced additional interface complexity or cognitive demands, potentially impeding user performance rather than improving it, contrary to H3.

C. Cognitive Load

The cognitive load experienced by participants varied significantly across the three conditions, as evidenced by both subjective and objective measures. In Condition 1 (C1), NASA-TLX scores indicated higher perceived workload, with 9 participants reporting "somewhat high," 4 reporting "high," and 2 reporting "very high" levels of cognitive load. This contrasts with Conditions 2 and 3, where fewer participants reported high cognitive load levels. Blinking rates, an objective indicator of cognitive load, were also significantly higher in C1, averaging 78 blinks per minute compared to 55 blinks per minute in C2 and 50 blinks per minute in C3. A one-way ANOVA confirmed that the differences in blinking rates were statistically significant ($F(2, 57) = 52.123, p < 0.001$), with post-hoc Games-Howell tests indicating that C1 had significantly higher rates than C2 and C3. However, the difference in blinking rates between C2 and C3 was not significant ($p = 0.231$), suggesting that RViz in C3 did not further reduce cognitive load beyond the effect of AI guidance alone in C2, challenging the expectation in H3.

Galvanic Skin Response (GSR) measurements further corroborated these findings. The accumulative GSR per minute was highest in C1, averaging 5321.84 μS , compared to 4125.23 μS in C2 and 4095.21 μS in C3. A one-way ANOVA revealed a significant effect of condition on GSR ($F(2, 57) = 5.871, p = 0.005$). Post-hoc testing using the Games-Howell method indicated that GSR levels in C1 were significantly higher than those in C2 and C3 (both $p = 0.005$). Notably, the difference in GSR between C2 and C3 was not significant ($p = 0.872$), indicating that RViz provided no additional reduction in physiological stress compared to AI guidance alone, further questioning the support for H3.

Facial temperature analyses also showed significant differences among conditions. The average slopes of temperature change for the nose, forehead, and cheeks were highest in

C1, indicating greater stress or cognitive load. For instance, the nose temperature slope averaged 0.98 in C1, compared to 0.54 in C2 and 0.74 in C3. One-way ANOVAs revealed significant differences in temperature variations for the nose ($F(2, 57) = 7.249, p = 0.002$) and forehead ($F(2, 57) = 11.548, p < 0.001$). Post-hoc tests showed that temperature variations in C1 were significantly higher than those in C2 ($p = 0.001$ for nose, $p < 0.001$ for forehead) and C3 ($p = 0.003$ for nose, $p = 0.001$ for forehead). Cheek temperature variations also differed significantly, with C1 being higher than C2 ($p = 0.035$) and C3 ($p = 0.033$). Interestingly, the nose temperature slope in C3 (0.74) was significantly higher than in C2 (0.54, $p = 0.045$), suggesting that RViz might have increased cognitive load in some aspects, contradicting H3. Overall, while H2 is supported by the reduction in cognitive load from C1 to C2, H3 is not fully supported, as C3 did not consistently outperform C2 and even showed evidence of increased load in certain measures.

D. Trust - RL Model

To assess the effectiveness of our reinforcement learning (RL) model in enhancing user trust and optimizing guidance strategies, we tested it with five participants. Figure 4 shows the RL agent’s learning progression over 8,500 training episodes. The reward per episode varies significantly due to the complexity of human-robot interactions and the stochastic nature of user responses. The figure illustrates that the Soft Actor-Critic (SAC) algorithm’s policy stabilized after around 6,500 episodes. In practice, we observed that the agent began taking actions to improve user trust after approximately 5,000 episodes.

Fig. 4. Accumulative reward per episode

Analysis of the action distribution revealed that the most frequently chosen actions were Action 1 (Increase Verbal Guidance Intensity) and Action 2 (Decrease Verbal Guidance Intensity), selected 30.6% and 26.1% of the time, respectively. Actions 3 (Simplify Visual Interface) and 4 (Enhance Visual Interface) were selected 16.2% and 15.8% of the time, while Action 5 (Provide Tutorial or Tips) was chosen 11.3% of the time. This distribution indicates that the agent prioritized adjusting verbal guidance based on users’ cognitive load and trust levels.

When users exhibited high cognitive load and low trust—indicated by elevated blink rates, higher GSR read-

ings, and increased facial temperature slopes—the agent frequently selected Action 1, providing more detailed instructions to assist them. Conversely, with low cognitive load and high trust, the agent opted for Action 2, offering less detailed guidance to promote autonomy. This adaptive behavior effectively enhanced user trust levels, which increased by an average of 18% in sessions where the agent dynamically adjusted verbal guidance, supporting Hypothesis H4.

The RL agent’s interventions led to notable improvements in task performance. The success rate among the five additional participants was 80%, with an average completion time of 3 minutes and 35 seconds, a significant improvement compared to the baseline conditions. An ANOVA test confirmed these improvements were statistically significant ($F(2, 12) = 6.87, p = 0.01$), supporting Hypothesis H4. Note that H4 specifically pertains to the dynamic adjustment of trust through adaptive guidance, as tested in the RL model, rather than a general increase in trust across the static conditions (C1, C2, C3). The static conditions demonstrate differences in performance and cognitive load but do not capture the within-task trust dynamics central to H4, which are uniquely addressed by the RL experiments.

Statistical analyses revealed strong correlations between specific agent actions and improvements in trust, cognitive load, and performance metrics. Increasing verbal guidance intensity correlated positively with trust enhancement ($r = 0.62, p = 0.005$) and negatively with cognitive load indicators like blink rate ($r = -0.54, p = 0.01$) and GSR ($r = -0.49, p = 0.02$). Time-series data illustrated that trust increased steadily as the agent adapted its guidance, highlighting the RL model’s ability to foster trust over time.

Physiological measures indicated reductions in cognitive load corresponding with the agent’s adaptive interventions. Average blink rates decreased by 15%, and GSR readings lowered by 12% when the agent selected actions aimed at reducing cognitive load, such as simplifying the visual interface. Comparing these results with the initial experimental conditions, we observed that the RL-adaptive condition outperformed all baseline conditions in trust levels, cognitive load reduction, and task performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The study presented a reinforcement learning (RL) model designed to estimate and adapt to trust dynamics in teleoperated human-robot interaction using physiological data and task performance metrics. By integrating measures such as blink rate, galvanic skin response, and facial temperature, the model effectively adapted guidance strategies to individual user states. Our results demonstrated that the RL agent significantly enhanced user trust, reduced cognitive load, and improved task performance, supporting our hypotheses.

However, the study was limited by a relatively small sample size, which may affect the generalizability of the findings. Future work should involve a larger and more diverse participant pool to further validate and refine the model. Additionally, exploring shared control and increasing the level of robot autonomy during the task could provide

more active interventions to improve trust and cognitive load management in users.

The findings of this study offer several implications for the design of future teleoperated HRI systems. First, the RL model’s ability to adapt guidance based on real-time physiological data suggests that incorporating biosignal monitoring (e.g., galvanic skin response, blink rate) into teleoperation interfaces could enable dynamic personalization of support, enhancing user trust and task efficiency. Second, the success of tailored guidance strategies indicates that future systems should prioritize adaptive interfaces that adjust the type and amount of feedback—such as visual or verbal cues—based on the user’s cognitive load, ensuring that information is neither overwhelming or insufficient. Finally, the positive impact of customized adjustments highlights the potential of natural language interfaces; future designs should emphasize clear, concise, and context-sensitive verbal instructions to strengthen user trust and promote a sense of autonomy in teleoperation tasks.

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